

Learning from Less: Synthetic Clinical Data Augmentation for Predicting Cardiac Decompensation and Pulmonary Exacerbation

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Abstract. Collecting prospective observational clinical data is a complex and resource-demanding process often involving direct patient contact, repeated follow-ups, and specialized data collection procedures. These challenges typically limit sample size and increase susceptibility to model overfitting. Synthetic data generation is a promising approach for augmenting limited clinical tabular data and improving generalization. In this study, we implement and benchmark different augmentation strategies to improve the identification of chronic patients' decompensation states based on physiological and clinical observations. The dataset comprises 117 patients and 284 visits, with repeated measurements capturing both decompensated and compensated states in heart failure or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Four data augmentation techniques were evaluated: a proposed Transformer-based Tabular Variational Autoencoder with Maximum Mean Discrepancy regularization and input masking (TTVAE-MMD), a Wasserstein GAN with gradient penalty, and two conventional interpolative and probabilistic approaches. Synthetic data quality was assessed using pyMDMA auditing library via (a) fidelity, (b) diversity, (c) authenticity, and (d) privacy metrics, along with analyses of marginal distributions and inter-feature correlations. TTVAE-MMD outperformed all other methods, achieving better diversity, fidelity, and privacy. Utility was assessed through the classification performance of a model optimised for each augmented subset, evaluated on entirely unseen individuals. The model trained on TTVAE-MMD augmented data reached the best F1-scores, representing a $\sim 14\%$ increase against real data baseline model. Findings show that high-quality synthetic data effectively augmented this small clinical dataset, improving model performance and generalization, with strong practical deployment potential.

Keywords: Data Augmentation · Synthetic Data Generation · Data Quality · Heart Failure · Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease.

1 Introduction

Heart Failure (HF) and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) are among the leading causes of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately 13% and 10% of all deaths, respectively [22]. These chronic conditions often lead to acute episodes, such as decompensation in HF or exacerbation in COPD, that significantly impair patient outcomes. Early detection of such events presents a critical opportunity for timely intervention and more effective disease management [13]. Recent studies have explored the use of Machine Learning (ML) models to support such early detection efforts [6,18]. However, these models typically require large, diverse and well-labeled datasets to achieve reliable predictive performance. In clinical settings, data collection faces several challenges that limit the availability of such datasets. Prospective observational studies, which are crucial for capturing acute episodes and disease progression, are inherently time-consuming and resource-intensive due to the need for direct patient interaction, repeated follow-ups, and specialized data collection protocols [6]. These constraints often result in datasets characterized by small sample sizes, class imbalance, missing or heterogeneous features, and the risk of overfitting when training ML models. Moreover, the logistical difficulties of recruiting and monitoring patients, especially in home and hospital environments, make large-scale data collection impractical [6].

To overcome these limitations, synthetic data generation techniques, particularly generative models such as Variational Autoencoders (VAE) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN), have gained attention as effective methods for data augmentation. By creating realistic synthetic samples, these approaches can enrich small clinical datasets, balance class distributions, and improve model generalization [9,19]. Data augmentation with synthetic samples holds promise for enhancing the robustness and accuracy of ML models in predicting critical events like decompensation or exacerbation, ultimately supporting better patient care and disease management.

In this study, we implement and benchmark various data augmentation strategies to improve the classification of decompensated versus compensated states in patients with chronic cardiac or pulmonary conditions, using physiological and clinical observations. The dataset, collected prospectively by the Consorci Sanitari Alt Penedès i Garraf (CSAPG) [6], includes 117 patients across 284 visits, with repeated measures capturing both hospital admissions (decompensated states) and home follow-ups (compensated states). The data is structured in tabular form encompassing demographics, clinical tests, sensor-derived physiological signals, and patient-reported symptoms collected before, during, and after a walking task. Our focus is on evaluating how different augmentation techniques can address data scarcity in this low-sample, high-dimensional clinical setting.

To augment the training data, we propose a Transformer-based Variational Autoencoder (TTVAE) that incorporates Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) as the divergence loss and leverages input masking during training. To benchmark our approach, we compare with a Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network with gradient penalty (WGAN) and two standard augmentation tech-

niques: Random Sampling (RS) and Synthetic Minority Oversampling technique (SMOTE). To assess the quality of the generated data, we also perform a comprehensive evaluation from two perspectives: (i) qualitative, via inspection of inter-attribute correlations and intra-attribute marginal distributions; and (ii) quantitative, to measure authenticity, privacy, fidelity, diversity, computed using the pyMDMA data auditing library [5]. The utility is assessed by (a) evaluating the decompensation state classifier trained on each augmented dataset, with hyperparameters tuned separately, to reflect a practical scenario where each approach is optimized for best performance, and (b) comparing feature importance rankings to the baseline, to determine how well the original feature hierarchies are preserved. Globally, the main contributions of this work are the following:

1. The proposal of input masking integration in the TTVAE with MMD loss architecture to generate synthetic data applied to small tabular clinical datasets;
2. The application of a domain-agnostic generative approach in clinical tabular data;
3. A comparative analysis of our generative model against three augmentation baselines: WGAN, RS and SMOTE;
4. A comprehensive evaluation procedure of synthetic data quality, combining qualitative inspection with quantitative metrics well-established in the literature, and their utility in training a decompensation state classifier.

2 Related Work

Recent advances in data augmentation techniques have led to significant developments of medical data analysis by enhancing diversity and improving model training in tabular domains [8]. Traditional oversampling methods like SMOTE are more effective in simpler settings, where the goal is to impute missing values or generate synthetic samples by interpolating between existing minority-class instances to balance class distributions as demonstrated in [24]. However, deep generative models such as VAEs, GANs and their variants can learn underlying data distributions and better capture complex feature dependencies, produce more realistic and diverse tabular data [3]. For example, Hameed and Alamgir [9] demonstrated how data augmentation can substantially optimize mortality prediction in patients with Acute Pancreatitis. By using small subsets from public sources (MIMIC-III, MIMIC-IV, and eICU), authors have employed advanced augmentation strategies such as SMOTE, VAEs and several tabular GAN variants (CTGAN, CopulaGAN, TGAN, CTAB-GAN). Models trained on augmented datasets significantly improved classifier performance, particularly in recall, a critical metric for identifying high-risk patients. Synthetic data generation for tabular medical datasets has also shown promising outcomes in the cardiovascular domain. For instance, Alqulaity and Yang [2] proposed an enhanced conditional GAN architecture designed to generate high-quality synthetic data from both continuous and categorical cardiovascular disease records. Beyond accuracy metrics alone, recent work highlights the need for rigorous,

multi-dimensional validation. A comprehensive review conducted by Vallevik et al. [20] introduced a conceptual framework combining statistical, usability, privacy, fairness, and computational dimensions for evaluating synthetic data quality in medical contexts. The authors noted most metrics are distance-based, focusing on statistical similarity, and emphasized the absence of clinical logic validation, such as assessment against medical knowledge or expert review. Hernandez et al. [11] evaluated the quality of synthetic tabular data generated from six healthcare-related datasets, defending that fidelity, utility and privacy assessment dimensions have been prioritized in recent literature. In a different study [12], the same authors have proposed a set of standardized and objective metrics integrated in a holistic framework to assess the same three quality dimensions and benchmark any synthetic data generation technique. However, their research also reveals a gap in explicitly validating medical relevance, which they identify as a key task for future work.

3 Methodology

3.1 Real-world Clinical Dataset

Data Characteristics A prospective observational clinical dataset was collected by CSAPG [6], from patients hospitalized in four different healthcare institutions (multi-center study), due to HF decompensation and COPD exacerbation and in follow-up home-monitoring visits. The dataset includes 135 patients with ages comprehended within 56 to 94 years old with 2.4 repeated measures across decompensated and compensated states, in average. A total of 18 patients were excluded due to data inconsistencies, resulting in a final dataset of 117 patients and 284 data collection sessions. Notable characteristics include incomplete follow-up across patients (28 single-session, 11 two-session, and 78 three-session patients) and demographic imbalance (75 male vs. 42 female patients). This dataset includes both discrete and continuous variables encompassing demographics, clinical test results, symptoms, and medication records, as well as additional data associated with walking and resting tasks captured during hospital admissions (classified as decompensated states) and two follow-up home visits (compensated states). A set of 24 features were used including sensor measurements such as heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), blood pressure (BP), and oxygen saturation (O2Sat) before, during and after the effort walking task. Additional observations consisted of patient-reports such as shortness of breath (Dyspnea), anxiety (Anxiety_Calm_4W) and body pain (Pain_Body), as well as clinical observations such as the distanced walked, reason for task ending, and if there was any technical assistance provided (see Figure 1).

Data Preprocessing From an initial set of 143 variables, 74 were retained by eliminating columns with >20% missing data, intentionally avoiding imputation to preserve the inherent sparsity characteristic of small medical datasets. The dimensionality was further reduced by excluding basal variables which did not

Fig. 1. Characterization of the clinical observational datasets under study.

change between different visits (e.g., clinical background, sociodemographics, lifestyle habits). The final set of data was, then, scaled using z-score normalization. Categorical features were one-hot encoded.

Data Partitioning A subset of 107 patients was selected for training and 10 for testing, based on clinical compatibility criteria to ensure homogeneity between groups and minimization of evaluation bias. This resulted in 254 samples for training (42.1% decompensated) and 30 for testing (33.3% decompensated). Within the training cohort, a 5-fold cross-validation optimization procedure was implemented, with 80% of the patients used for model training and 20% for validation in each fold.

3.2 Synthetic Data Augmentation

Proposed Method: TTVAE-MMD We propose a TTVAE, inspired by the work of Wang and Nguyen [21], that combines the power of self-attention with a MMD regularizer and input masking to encourage both faithful reconstruction and diverse generalization. Original source code is available here. The architecture was adapted to include input masking, as illustrated in Figure 2. Instead of the traditional Kullback-Leibler divergence term, we adopted an MMD loss due to its variance stability and posterior collapse mitigation that would, in the end, lead to more informative latent representations and improved generative quality [23]. The adapted loss function is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{TTVAE}} = -E_{q(z|x)} [\log p(x|z)] + \beta \cdot \text{MMD}(q(z), p(z)),$$

where $-E_{q(z|x)} [\log p(x|z)]$ is the reconstruction term, $\text{MMD}(q(z), p(z))$ represents the MMD score computed between the posterior $q(z)$ and the prior $p(z)$ distributions, and β is the strength factor given to the MMD term to promote a more disentangled latent space. In addition, to force the model generalization and generative diversity, we also applied input masking. During training, a fraction of the input features is randomly masked at each epoch, forcing the model to infer missing information from context and thereby reducing overfitting [10]. Figure 2 depicts the encoder-decoder architecture, reparameterization, masking strategy, and combined loss function.

Table 1. Best hyperparameters selected through randomized search for each synthetic data generation architecture defined.

Architecture	Parameter	Search Range	Best parameter
TTVAE-MMD	<i>embedding_dim</i>	{256, 512, 1024}	512
	<i>learning_rate</i>	{1e-5, 5e-5, 1e-4, 5e-4}	5e-4
	<i>beta_max</i>	{1, 2, 3}	2
	<i>input_mask_prob</i>	{0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9}	0.5
	<i>batch_size</i>	{16, 64, 128}	64
	<i>epochs</i>	{200, 500, 700}	200
	<i>early_stopping</i>	60	60
WGAN	<i>latent_dim</i>	{256, 512, 1024}	512
	<i>learning_rate</i>	{1e-5, 5e-5, 1e-4}	5e-5
	<i>critic_iter</i>	{3, 5, 10}	3
	<i>gradient_penalty_factor</i>	{2, 5, 10}	5
	<i>batch_size</i>	{16, 64, 128}	16
	<i>epochs</i>	{200, 500, 700}	200
	<i>early_stopping</i>	60	60

3.3 Evaluation

Synthetic Data Quality Evaluation The quality of the generated data was assessed in two perspectives: (1) qualitative, and (2) quantitative. Qualitative analysis includes the inspection of (a) inter-attribute correlation matrices, (b) intra-attribute marginal distributions. Quantitative analysis covers four key dimensions: (i) authenticity, assessing generalisation by testing for record memorization, i.e., whether synthetic instances are statistically distinguishable from real records [1], (ii) privacy, using Distance to Closest Record (DCR) to estimate the risk of real data leakage [15], (iii) fidelity, measuring the alignment between synthetic and real data distributions [16], and (iv) diversity, capturing variability of generated data and its ability to represent the breadth of real-world data patterns [16]. All scores were computed using distance-based metrics from the pyMDMA library (code available here) [5]. To assess the overall quality, we computed the polygon area assuming each metric is a vertex. The formula is defined as:

$$\text{Global Quality (\%)} = \frac{100\%}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N r_i \cdot r_{(i \bmod 4)+1}, \quad r_{N+1} = r_1$$

where $r_i \in [0, 1]$ are the normalized metric values and N the number of dimensions ($N = 4$ in this study). These quantitative dimensions were selected as they bring complementary perspectives of the generated data quality and most of them share contrastive trade-off relationships with each other, allowing us to assess the ideal quality scenario for each dataset. All metrics are defined in %, representing the amount of generated samples that are meet the criteria.

ML Utility Evaluation To assess the utility impact of each data augmentation strategy, we defined a clinically relevant downstream ML task: binary classification of the compensated vs. decompensation patient state in each visit. Utility is defined as the classification performance of a model trained on the augmented dataset. The choice of the ML algorithm and hyperparameters are optimized, with a grid-guided cross-validation training scheme (see Figure 3), separately for each augmentation method. The hyperparameter search space is described in Table 2.

Table 2. Hyperparameter search space of the pre-defined classification models.

Algorithm	Parameter	Search Range
SVM	C	{0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100}
	$kernel$	{linear, rbf, poly, sigmoid}
	$degree$	{2, 3, 4}
	$gamma$	{scale, auto}
KNN	$n_neighbors$	{3, 5, 7, 9}
	$weights$	{uniform, distance}
	$algorithm$	{auto, ball_tree, kd_tree, brute}
RF	$n_estimators$	{10, 50, 100, 200}
	max_depth	{None, 10, 20, 30}
	$min_samples_split$	{0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5}
	$min_samples_leaf$	{0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.5}
LGBM	max_depth	{None, 10, 20, 30}
	$n_estimators$	{10, 50, 100, 200}
	$min_samples_split$	{2, 5, 10, 50}
	$min_samples_leaf$	{1, 2, 4, 50}
XGB	$learning_rate$	{0.01, 0.1, 0.2}
	$n_estimators$	{10, 50, 100, 200}
	max_depth	{None, 10, 20, 30}
	$min_samples_split$	{0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5}
NB	$min_samples_leaf$	{0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.5}
	$learning_rate$	{0.01, 0.1, 0.2}
NB	$var_smoothing$	{1e-9, 1e-8, 1e-7}

SVM – Support Vector Machine; **KNN** – K-Nearest Neighbors;
RF – Random Forest; **LGBM** – Light Gradient Boosting Machine;
XGB – eXtreme Gradient Boosting; **NB** – Naive Bayes

For each model, the classification threshold was determined by selecting the point on the ROC curve that maximizes Youden’s J statistic, balancing sensitivity and specificity. Balanced accuracy (BA, i.e. macro-avg. recall), macro-avg. F1-score, and the Area Under the ROC curve (AUROC) scores were computed to assess the utility dimension. Importantly, final evaluation was performed on a patient-disjoint test set to ensure generalization to entirely unseen individuals and avoid information leakage. This benchmarking approach reflects a practical use case where each augmentation technique is integrated into a full predictive pipeline and tuned for maximum effectiveness. To assess and compare feature relevance, permutation importance scores were computed for each of the final

Fig. 3. Illustration of the ML utility evaluation scheme.

trained models. To enable comparison across augmentation strategies, feature importance was evaluated on the top 10 features identified by the baseline model.

4 Results

This section is organized in two parts. First, we assess the quality of the synthetic datasets produced by each augmentation method. Second, we examine how these augmented datasets influence downstream classification performance on the held-out test set.

4.1 Synthetic Data Quality Evaluation

We first compared the one-dimensional marginal distributions of continuous and categorical features across the original and synthetic datasets (Figure 4). All methods broadly capture the main patterns of the original distributions, but RS mostly fails to reproduce categorical variables, while SMOTE produces more identical and smoothed distributions.

Next, we inspected the inter-feature correlation matrices (Figure 5). While TTVAE-MMD and SMOTE recover the dominant correlations present in the real data, RS ignores joint variability and WGAN ends up adding non-existent pairwise associations (real data extrapolation).

The quantitative inspection is depicted by Table 3, and summarizes five metric scores namely, authenticity, privacy, fidelity, diversity, and global quality, computed with distance-based metrics from pyMDMA. TTVAE-MMD achieves the most balanced trade-off between fidelity and privacy (authenticity 51.0%, privacy 94.7%, fidelity 93.9%, diversity 79.5%). WGAN offers slightly higher authenticity (67.5%) but lower fidelity (83.1%) and diversity (58.3%). Random Sampling maximizes privacy (99.6%) at the cost of fidelity (35.7%). In contrast, SMOTE obtains perfect fidelity (100.0%) but zero privacy preservation (0.0%). The Global Quality score also indicates the TTVAE-MMD is the best data generator for this dataset by achieving 63.1%.

Fig. 4. Marginal distributions illustrating intra-feature relationships for different data generation strategies. Synthetic data is displayed in green and real data in grey color.

Fig. 5. Correlation matrices illustrating inter-feature relationships for different data generation strategies. Lighter pixels indicate higher correlations and vice-versa.

Table 3. Synthetic data quality evaluation metrics for every method proposed. Best individual metrics are underscored and the best global technique is highlighted.

Generative Methods	Data Quality Scores (%)				
	Authenticity (\uparrow)	Privacy (\uparrow)	Fidelity (\uparrow)	Diversity (\uparrow)	Global Quality (\uparrow)
<i>TTVAE-MMD</i>	51.0	94.7	93.9	79.5	63.1
<i>WGAN</i>	67.5	94.6	83.1	58.3	57.6
<i>Random Sampling</i>	<u>92.0</u>	<u>99.6</u>	35.7	74.4	55.6
<i>SMOTE</i>	0.0	0.0	<u>100.0</u>	<u>98.0</u>	24.5

4.2 ML Utility Evaluation

ML Utility is framed as impact of these new synthetic samples in the patterns learned by a classification model and evaluated by the performance on a test set containing real data from held-out patients. Table 4 reports the predictive performance scores obtained on the testing set after training each model using a 5-fold cross-validation scheme. The baseline model, trained and optimized for real data only, achieves 67.0% macro F1-score, 67.5% balanced accuracy and 73.0% of area under the ROC curve. Augmenting with TTVAE-MMD boosts all the performance metrics, with macro F1-score increasing substantially to 80.7%. WGAN and SMOTE reveals intermediate gains (73.0% and 68.1%, respectively), while RS degrades all performance metrics, producing a macro F1-score of 47.5%.

Table 4. Assessment of the predictive performance of decompensation classification trained with only real data (baseline) versus augmented datasets.

Dataset Source	Best Algorithm	Performance Scores (%)		
		F1-Score	BA	AUROC
<i>Baseline</i>	RF	67.0	67.5	73.0
<i>TTVAE-MMD</i>	RF	80.7	80.0	77.0
<i>WGAN</i>	SVM_{linear}	73.0	72.5	73.5
<i>Random Sampling</i>	SVM_{poly}	47.5	47.5	39.0
<i>SMOTE</i>	SVM_{rbf}	68.3	70.0	79.0

BA – Balanced Accuracy; AUROC – Area Under the ROC curve.

Fig. 6. Permutation scores of each final model trained for the top 10 features ranked as most important by the baseline model.

Figure 6 compares the permutation scores of the top 10 most important features obtained when training on the real data (baseline) and their values for the final models trained under each augmentation method. In the Baseline model, the blood oxygen saturation after (*After_O2Sat*) and before (*Before_O2Sat*) the walking task emerge as the two most important predictive variables, followed

by the presence of dyspnea before (*Before_Dyspnea_Class*) and body pain during the walking exercise (*During_Pain_Body*). The TTVAE-MMD synthetic data largely preserves similar ordering, as *Before_O2Sat* emerges as the single most important feature, with *After_O2Sat* and the pain/dyspnea variables being ranked in very similar positions. In contrast, the model trained with the WGAN synthetic set distorts the feature importance map. Even though *Before_O2Sat* still presents very high permutation score, almost all other features receive near-zero (or even slightly negative) importance, indicating that the WGAN relies in a different set of features, ignoring most of the original predictors. RS produces a very noisy feature importance profile, for the 10 features selected, with several features laying around zero or flipping sign. No clear ranking emerges, and strong predictors from the real data are substantially down-weighted. Lastly, SMOTE raises moderate importance scores across most features ranked by baseline model, but two of them, specifically pain complaints *Before_Pain_Body* and the heart-rate before the walking test (*Before_HR*) shifted to negative values.

Fig. 7. Radar charts illustrating the assessment of synthetic data quality under multiple dimensions. The ML Utility vertex is defined by the F1-score (macro).

The radar charts presented in Figure 7, enable an intuitive visualization of the synthetic data quality profiles, reflected in the four quantitative metrics, and ML utility (via macro F1-score in the decompensation classification models), for each data augmentation method. We can observe that, globally, the TTVAE-MMD reaches the best possible data quality trade-off compared with the remaining methods, as it covers a wider radar area, followed by WGAN. SMOTE and RS cover opposite areas of the radar spectrum, as expected.

5 Discussion

Our work focused on exploring data augmentation techniques suitable for increasing the performance and generalization ability of a ML model trained on a small clinical tabular dataset, with the goal of classifying disease state as decompensated or compensated. Given the clinical context, achieving a balance between enhancing diversity in the dataset, while avoiding to copy real data points, maintaining the realism of the data is also crucial.

In terms of synthetic data quality, our findings suggest the proposed TTVAE-MMD provides the most balanced synthetic data, preserving the original dataset’s structure with realistic distributions and inter-feature correlations. Quantitatively, it achieved high fidelity, diversity, privacy, and a comparatively lower authenticity score. This likely reflects the metric’s sensitivity to pattern similarity rather than memorization. In small datasets, faithful replication of sparse and structured patterns can reduce perceived novelty, highlighting a trade-off between realism and authenticity. It also achieved strong ML utility, preserving original feature hierarchies. These results suggest that combining MMD regularization with input masking provides a powerful inductive bias for generating high-quality synthetic tabular data. WGAN also achieved competitive results, showing the second-highest utility score and a reasonable fidelity/privacy trade-off. However, it did not accurately reproduce feature correlations and demonstrated reduced diversity, likely due to mode collapse or other instabilities commonly encountered during GAN training. Among the interpolative and probabilistic approaches, SMOTE showed perfect fidelity and diversity but lacked authenticity and privacy resulting in only moderate utility, which reflects its deterministic nature and limited capacity to generalize beyond the input data. RS maximized privacy and authenticity but performed poorly in terms of fidelity and utility, highlighting its inability to model complex data distributions. These observations are consistent with findings reported in previous studies, such as [4,17,14], which also demonstrate the potential of deep generative models to outperform traditional augmentation methods in tabular domains.

Regarding predictive performance in the patient decompensation detection task, the incorporation of synthetic data via TTVAE-MMD led to the most significant improvement, consistent with earlier findings on generated data quality. While WGAN and SMOTE provided moderate gains, their performance metrics confirmed lower reliability compared to the transformer-based approach. In particular, the WGAN feature importance profile deviated significantly from the baseline, suggesting that the learned representations were less aligned with the true predictive structure of the real data. As anticipated, RS demonstrated the weakest performance. Overall, TTVAE-MMD stands out as the most effective method for synthetic data generation in this clinical classification context.

Despite the promising results obtained through synthetic data augmentation in this small-cohort study, several important limitations must be acknowledged. First, the dataset is limited in size (117 patients), presents demographic imbalance (75 males vs. 42 females), includes a variable number of visits per patient, and combines two distinct clinical conditions. Second, visits were treated as

independent samples, which simplifies modeling but overlooks potential inpatient temporal dependencies. Third, the utility assessment was restricted to traditional machine learning classifiers, which may not fully capture the predictive potential of the dataset. Lastly, although a held-out test set was used to evaluate generalization, its small size (10 patients, 30 visits) may limit the robustness of performance estimates.

Future work will focus on addressing the current study’s limitations and further validating the proposed approach. A first step involves conducting formal ablation studies to disentangle the contributions of individual components (e.g., input masking) within the augmentation pipeline. This will help clarify which architectural or training elements of TTVAE-MMD are most responsible for gains in model utility and data quality. In parallel, a nested cross-validation framework will be implemented to provide fold-aggregated performance estimates and reduce the risk of biased evaluation due to small sample size. To improve fairness and support subgroup analyses, we plan to extend the generative model to condition data generation based on specific attributes such as gender, age, or any clinical constraints. This would enable targeted balancing of demographic groups or the generation of clinically meaningful scenarios for interpretation. To assess the plausibility of the generated samples, clinicians can help define sets of rules that distinguish clinically acceptable from non-acceptable records (e.g., oxygen saturation over 100%). This would add an additional trust layer using clinically validated knowledge. Finally, to assess generalisation power and benchmark effectiveness more broadly, we intend to test the proposed augmentation, particularly the input masking adaptation, method on larger public datasets by simulating small-sample settings and evaluating how well synthetic data recover the structure and predictive patterns of the full cohort.

6 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the feasibility to augment a small, structured clinical dataset with synthetically generated samples without compromising the privacy, fidelity, or diversity of the data, and meaningfully improving downstream classification performance. In a practical clinical application, augmenting the training data with samples from our proposed TTVAE-MMD increased the balanced accuracy by 12.5%, highlighting the potential of generative models to enhance generalization in small-data machine learning tasks. TTVAE-MMD achieved a favorable balance across key quality metrics, with privacy (94.7%), fidelity (93.9%), and diversity (79.5%) scores that outperformed or matched baseline methods. In contrast, WGAN failed to match the diversity of the original data, SMOTE generated copies of the real data with diminished authenticity and privacy, and Random Sampling showed reduced fidelity and utility. Moreover, classifiers trained with TTVAE-MMD data relied on similar feature importance profiles to those trained on real data, indicating that clinically meaningful patterns were preserved. While these results are preliminary, they provide strong evidence for the feasibility of using synthetic tabular data to address the challenges

of small-sample clinical research. We anticipate that such approaches will become increasingly valuable in studies where data collection is resource-intensive, time-consuming, and reliant on specialized human effort. Generative augmentation methods like TTVAE-MMD have the potential to support more reliable model development and increase confidence in clinical ML applications, particularly in observational settings with constrained datasets.

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